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SHANS - LOOKING BACK AND BEYOND: FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE LICENSURE EXAM PERFORMANCE FOR MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE AND PHARMACY

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Abstract:

This study aimed to determine factors that influence the licensure exam performance of Saint Mary's University in the 2 board programs under the School of Health and Natural Sciences. The two programs include BS Medical Laboratory Science and BS Pharmacy. It covers the period from 2016 to 2023 which includes the graduates starting from SY 2016-2017 who were then the first batch of licensure exam takers, until the graduates of SY 2021-2022 who took the latest licensure exams (November 2022 for Pharmacy and March 2023 for Medical Laboratory Science). A retrospective review of the academic performance of the licensure exam takers based on the records from the Registrar, Dean's Office, Guidance and Testing Office and Department Heads were conducted. Predictors of the licensure examination performance rating of the exam takers based on their academic profile (CET score, GWA in college, Internship rating and Integrated Course Rating) were identified. The trend for the Institutional Licensure Exam Performance Rating for the 2 programs for the inclusive years were as well determined and correlated with the study participants' assessment on the quality of curriculum and instruction during their undergraduate for the courses included in the licensure exam. The quality of curriculum was assessed based on the (1) attainment of course objectives, (2) coverage of the contents of the course, (3) quality of instructional materials used, (4) teacher's mastery of the subject matter, and (5) relevance of course assignments/requirements. The quality of instruction was assessed through (1) instructional procedures employed by faculty, (2) course requirements, (3) sources of written exercises administered by faculty, and (4) availability of learning facilities. Strengths and opportunities for improvement were identified based on the qualitative responses of the study participants to the formulated questions.

For the academic profile of the exam takers, majority of the MTLE and PhLE takers got scores of 90 and above in their CET scores and with GWA of below 87 when they graduated in their programs. Most of the MTLE takers had an internship rating and integrated course rating within 80-89 bracket while the PhLE takers had their internship ratings mostly within the 90-100 bracket and within the 75-70 bracket for the integrated course rating. CET score, GWA, Internship Rating and Integrated Course Rating are predictors of MTLE performance rating. The same predictors were identified for the PhLE except for the Integrated Course Rating. Generally, the IPRs gained for MTLE were below the NPR. Out of the 13 MTLE batches, there were only 3 where the IPRs gained were above the NPRs with the highest rating gained in the latest MTLE. The IPRs gained for the PhLE were of inconsistent trend from the start but above NPR ratings were consistent in the 4 most recent PhLEs. In the assessment of quality factors for curriculum, the MTLE and PhLE takers assessed that

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that across all the professional courses in their respective curriculum, the following are very important factors to be considered to be able to pass the exam: attainment of course objectives, coverage of the contents of the course, quality of instructional materials used, teachers' mastery and the relevance of course assignments and requirements. On the other hand, on the assessment of quality factors for instruction, the MTLE and PhLE takers assessed the following as "often" for each of the professional courses included in the licensure exams: degree of practiced by the faculty of the indicated instructional procedures, degree of implementation of the indicated course requirements and degree of which the indicated sources of written exercises are used by the faculty. As to the degree of importance of the availability of learning facilities that helped them in passing the exam for each of the professional courses, the MTLE and PhLE takers rated the factors generally as "important". No significant correlation have been found between the IPR and the study participants's assessment on the factors for the quality of curriculum and instruction for both programs. This finding is attributed to the limited number of representatives per batch of examinees who participated in the study, that is why the overall assessment of the quality factors in relation to the IPR may not be well captured in the analysis. The best contributions of SMU to the MTLE and PhLE exam takers think have helped them pass the licensure exams were on the following areas: instructors, review classes and seminar lectures, facilities, instruction, internship, independent learning and SMU branding. The opportunities for improvement identified by the MTLE and PhLE exam takers that SMU should take into consideration are on the following areas: instructors and their delivery of instruction, review classes and seminar lectures, and facilities.

Keywords: Board Exam Performance, Curriculum, Instruction, Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

The School of Health and Natural Sciences of Saint Mary's University conducts researches which shall become basis for the improvement of its services under the Research Project "SHANS – Looking Back and Beyond 2021-2026" (SLBB 2021-2026). This research project of the school starts in SY 2022-2023 until SY 2025-2026 wherein every year, the SHANS should be able to produce researches that will look into the challenges that the school faced in previous years and come up with solutions to address such challenges based on the findings of the researches conducted. It also covers evaluation of existing projects or programs which shall serve as basis for enhancing the programs or projects or crafting of better alternative programs/projects. The SLBB Research Project is included in the research agenda of SHANS to have researches which will serve as support in the implementation of its programs or projects aligned with the Strategic Plan 2021-2026. This study was the first project conducted under the SLBB. It is a retrospective review of the licensure exam performance of the two board programs which celebrated their 10th Anniversary this SY 2022-2023, the Bachelor in Medical Laboratory Science (BMLS) and the Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy (BSP).

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The Licensure Exam Performance is regarded one of the measures for the quality of education that a university or a school provides. A high passing rate in the Licensure Exam is always on the top goal of a school because it mirrors the kind of education received by the graduates from the institution (Pasia et al., 2012). Graduates then are challenged to perform at par or above the national passing rate (Estrada, Pariñas, Mendoza, Defiño, Panghulan, 2021) for them to be regarded as highly competent (Pasia et al., 2012). Hence, academic institutions conduct various correlational studies with licensure examination performances to determine what areas or factors have to be focused on in order to improve the percentage of graduates passing the exam.

In Saint Mar's University (SMU), the Bachelor of Medical Laboratory Science Program (BMLS) and the Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy Program (BSP) were offered in SY 2012-2013 and had their first batch of licensure exam takers in 2016. Through the years, it was observed that the passings rates were not consistent. There were times when the passings rates were high and sometimes these were low. As per record, there were no comprehensive studies conducted to look into the different aspects behind these results. Hence, a study that shall dwell on licensure exam performance is a need to come up with concrete solutions to whatever opportunities for improvement shall be found with the ultimate goal of improving the passing rates of the 2 programs in future licensure exams. It is along this premise that this study is contextualized.

Analytical Framework and Research Paradigm

Competence in academic performance of different academic institutions is typically rated through licensure exam rating (Balansag & Marasigan, 2019) and several studies on this context in the health allied sciences support this claim. In the study of Banua (2017) regarding the factors affecting the performance of Bicol University graduates in the Nurses' Licensure Examination (NLE), academic performance was found to be the best predictor in the NLE. Similar results were found in Oducado, Cendaña and Delariarte (2019) wherein factors such as High School Grade General Average, College Grade General Weighted Average and scores in College Admission Test, Nursing Aptitude Test, and Pre-board Examination were significantly correlated with NLE rating for the Nursing graduates of West Visayas State University. From the Medical Technology graduates of a selected university in the Philippines, Cabanban (2017) noted "substantial" correlation between academic performance and board examination results. In a more recent study, Estrada et al. (2021) found that Academic Performance significantly predicts Licensure Performance among the graduates of BMLS in the Adventist University of the Philippines and all the six subjects in the board examination were significantly correlated individually with academic performance. The findings imply that when Academic Performance is increased, board rating also increases. Talaroc, Ali and Alipio (2021) investigated the factors influencing the licensure examination performance of Radiologic Technology (RT) graduates in a private higher education institution (HEI) in Northern Mindanao, Philippines and found that academic performance in terms of Student Internship Grade (SIG), College Admission Test (CAT), and Terminal Competency Assessment (TCA) scores were significant factors affecting the licensure examination performance of the RT graduates. Even in measuring the preparedness of health allied science graduates to pass certain foreign government

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standard tests for employment, academic performance is one of the parameters found to be a significant factor. In the study of [Dayaganon and Limjoco \(2016\)](#) of the Medical Technology/ Medical Laboratory Science (MT/MLS) graduates in Region XI seeking employment abroad, they investigated the preparedness of the graduates to American Society for Clinical Pathology (ASCP) and found that there is a significant direct, high correlation between the MT/MLS graduates' academic performance and their preparedness to ASCP examination, implying that an increase in academic performance of the graduates corresponds to an increase in their level of preparedness to ASCP examination. Licensure exams in other countries are also associated with academic performance. [Buraphadecha, S., Chinwong, D., Thiankhanitikun, K. \(2018\)](#) identified predictors of Pharmacy Licensure Exam (PLE) using grade point averages (GPAs) in a university in Thailand. Significant relations were found between MCQ and pharmacotherapy, pharmaceutical technology and integration of pharmacy professions, and between OSPE and pharmacy practices II. The association of admissions route and specialty track with OSPE was slight. The study identified three course sub-areas: pharmacotherapy, pharmaceutical technology and integration of pharmacy professions as strong predictors of high MCQ scores suggesting that high GPAs improved high MCQ scores. [Spivey, Burns and Johnson \(2020\)](#) found that unsatisfactory academic performance was associated with decreased likelihood of passing the North American Pharmacist Licensure Examination (NAPLEX) and in the systematic review of predictors of success for the NAPLEX, [Park, Philips, and Pavuluri, \(2021\)](#), found the following to be positively correlated factors: Pharmacy College Admission Test (PCAT) scores, cumulative pharmacy school grade point average (GPA), overall Pharmacy Curriculum Outcomes Assessment (PCOA) scores, and PCOA content areas scores.

Aside from academic performance, there are other factors which may contribute to the success of licensure exams. [Dayaday \(2018\)](#) assessed faculty/teaching strategy, curriculum, instructional materials, facilities/laboratory equipment/laboratory activities, admission and retention policy, review preparation and mental/study behavior through survey. The results revealed that faculty and instructional materials favorably affect the performance of the examinees. Passers attributed their success to curriculum, admission, retention policy and their own study behavior. Poor performance of the examinees was attributed to lack of laboratory facilities/equipment. In the study of [Delos Angeles \(2019\)](#), curriculum and quality of instruction factors were used to determine success for board exam performance (LET). Results revealed that the general education components of the curriculum are the most influential in the graduates' licensure examination performance and relevant instructional tasks and sound assessment procedures in both general education and professional education courses lead to more chances of success in the board exam. It was further discussed in the study that students will learn best when curriculum and instruction are congruent with that of the learner's particular needs. Teacher factor plays a pivoting role in effective learning as the teachers' educational qualifications and personal qualities can indeed affect teaching efficiency and develop authentic human relationships with students. On the other hand, student factor depends upon the behavior, attitude and interest of the students developed prior to their attendance to tertiary school until these attributes could be carried on and enhance through experience in college life to be prepared to take full advantage of a

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wide variety of intellectually stimulating and demanding contexts thereby increasing their competence. In the most recent study of [Delos Angeles \(2020\)](#), the quality of the process variables namely curriculum and instruction were assessed to best predict the performance of the Teacher Education graduates of a university in Cagayan Valley, Philippines. The results of the study revealed that variables clustered along the quality of curriculum and qualities of instruction are the variables most significantly related to LET performance. Attainment of course objectives, the relevance of course requirements and mastery of the subject matter were the curriculum variables significantly related to LET performance. On instructional quality, the relevance of written requirements and performance of instructors are highly significant to LET performance. The strongest predictors of LET performance identified in the study are professors' mastery of the subject matter and the quality of the content of the general education courses.

This study deals with identifying factors that influence the performance in licensure exams for the BMLS and BSP programs for the graduates of SY 2016-2017 to SY 2021-2022. The focus is on academic performance, and on the quality of curriculum and instruction. Academic performance is included as this is a parameter that mirrors the quality of the takers in terms of their individual inclination to academic excellence as cited in various studies. Curriculum and instruction are included since these two institutional factors are regarded to be influential in the success of licensure exams ([Delos Angeles, 2019](#)). Results of the study shall become the basis of recommendations for the admission and retention policies or the conduct of review and revisions as needed and intervention programs on curriculum and instruction.

This study was guided by the research paradigm presented in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. Research Paradigm

The individual *Licensure Exam Performance Ratings* of the Exam Takers were obtained in a retrospective review of the on-hand results from the PRC and were correlated with the factors on academic performance which includes the *College Entrance Test score (CET score)* as pre-admission profile; the *GWA in college, Internship Rating* and *Integrated Course Rating*. These variables are deemed necessary to determine the attributes of the exam takers when they were admitted in the program and their academic standing, competence in clinical practice when they graduated and readiness to take the licensure exam. The academic performance factors identified as predictors that influence the exam takers' licensure exam performance rating were used as basis for recommendations on the existing admission and retention policies of the two programs.

The *Institutional Licensure Exam Performance Rating* for the 2 programs for the inclusive years were determined from PRC results and were correlated with the study participants' assessment on the quality of curriculum and instruction during their undergraduate for the courses included in the licensure exam. The *quality of curriculum* was assessed based on the (1) attainment of course objectives, (2) coverage of the contents of the course, (3) quality of instructional materials used, (4) teacher's mastery of the subject matter, and (5) relevance of course assignments/requirements. The *quality of instruction* was assessed through (1) instructional procedures employed by faculty, (2) course requirements, (3) sources of written exercises administered by faculty, and (4) availability of learning facilities. *Strengths and opportunities for improvement* were identified based on the qualitative responses of the study participants to the formulated questions. The institutional factors identified that influence the institutional licensure exam performance rating and those from the qualitative responses of the study participants served as springboard for intervention programs on curriculum and instruction to achieve high rating in future licensure exams.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to identify factors that influence the licensure exam performance of SMU in Medical Laboratory Science and Pharmacy from the graduates of SY 2016-2017 to SY 2021-2022. The following are the specific objectives:

1. To determine the profile of the exam takers in a retrospective review of their:

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- a. Licensure Exam Performance Rating
- b. Academic Profile
 - b.1 Pre-admission profile (CET score)
 - b.2 GWA in college
 - b.3 Internship Rating
 - b.4 Integrated Course Rating
2. To determine the academic profile variables that predict the Licensure Exam Performance Rating of the exam takers.
3. To determine the trend in the Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate of the 2 board programs for the inclusive years indicated.
4. To identify institutional factors that influenced the trend in the Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate of the 2 board programs based on the study participants' assessment on the following:
 - a. Quality of Curriculum based on
 - a.1 attainment of course objectives
 - a.2 coverage of the contents of the course
 - a.3 quality of instructional materials used
 - a.4 teachers mastery of the subject matter
 - a.5 relevance of course assignments/requirements
 - b. Quality of Instruction through
 - b.1 instructional procedures employed by faculty
 - b.2 course requirements
 - b.3 sources of written exercises administered by faculty
 - b.4 availability of learning facilities
5. To determine significant correlation between Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate and the study participants' assessment on curriculum and instruction.
6. To identify strengths and opportunities for improvement to achieve high rating in future licensure exams.

Hypotheses:

1. The academic profile variables do not significantly predict the Licensure Exam Performance Rating of the exam takers.
2. There is no significant correlation between the trend in the Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate and the study participants' assessment on curriculum and instruction.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive-correlation design as employed in the study of [Delos Angeles \(2020\)](#) mixed with qualitative approach. The descriptive approach is used to characterize the

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profile of the licensure exam takers based on a retrospective review of their academic performance variables and in visually graphing the trend in licensure exam performance of the 2 programs in the inclusive years indicated. Inferential approach was used in determining the academic performance profile as predictors of the licensure exam rating of the exam takers. Correlational approach was employed in determining relationship between the trend in institutional licensure exam performance rating of the 2 programs and the institutional factors that focus on the assessment of the study participants on curriculum and instruction. Qualitative approach was used in analyzing the responses of the study participants on the two questions that dealt with strengths and opportunities for improvement.

Research Locale

This study was done in Saint Mary's University, particularly in the School of Health and Natural Sciences which is in-charge of the BMLS and BSP programs.

Participants and Sample Size

There are two definitions of the participants in this study. In the first and second objectives of the study which include a retrospective review of the licensure exam rating and academic profile of the exam takers and identifying predictors, the list of exam takers who passed the board exam based on the PRC records are referred to as "exam takers" being the study participants. These exam takers summed up to 176 PhLE and 220 MTLE takers for the inclusive years of this study.

In the 4th, 5th and 6th objectives of the study which deals on determining institutional factors affecting the trend in licensure exam of the 2 programs and seeking responses on strengths and opportunities for improvement, only the exam passers who willingly and voluntarily answered the questionnaire on the assessment of the quality of curriculum and instructions are referred to as the "study participants". These participants summed up to 35 PhLE and 68 MTLE takers.

The non-passers were excluded because a study of similar context shall be conducted later along the area involving perspectives for non-passers.

Research Instrument

This study used a researcher-made instrument that is patterned from the variables used in the study of [Delos Angeles \(2020\)](#), suiting it into the context of the BMLS and BSP programs. The variables used are generic in context and believed to be relevant and highly applicable to the BMLS and BSP programs. The crafted tool is made of 6 parts (*see Annex A & B: The Research Questionnaire for MedTech and for Pharmacy*) that involve assessment of the study participants on curriculum and instruction during their undergraduate for the courses included in the licensure exam. Part I includes an assessment of the quality of curriculum based on the (1) attainment of course objectives, (2) coverage of the contents of the course, (3) quality of instructional materials used, (4) teacher's mastery of the subject matter, and (5) relevance of course assignments/requirements. Part II is an assessment of the quality of instruction through instructional procedures employed by faculty. Part III involves assessment of the quality of instruction through course requirements. Part IV is on assessment of the quality of instruction through sources of written exercises administered by

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faculty. Part V deals with assessment of the quality of instruction through availability of learning facilities, a parameter which is not used in [Delos Angeles \(2020\)](#) but is added in this study as it is believed to be a relevant variable for instruction. Part VI, the last part, is the section on strengths and opportunities for improvement which has two questions to be answered by the study participants.

The crafted questionnaire was evaluated by the faculty of the BMLS and BSP programs prior to the conduct of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Determination of Licensure Exam Rating and Academic Performance Profile

The Licensure Exam Rating of each of the exam takers were obtained from the Dean's Office /Department Head's files of PRC results. The academic performance profile which include the pre-admission profile such as CET score was obtained from the Guidance and Testing Office. The GWA in College was obtained from the Registrar's Office while the Internship Rating and the Integrated Course Rating were obtained from the internship instructors and department heads.

Determination of the Trend in the Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate

The data from PRC was used to determine the trend in the Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate of the 2 programs. The trend was presented through a graph to visualize the trend through the years.

Floating of Research Questionnaire

The research questionnaires were sent to the study participants on line using a Google Form. No face-to-face gathering of data was done.

Treatment of Data

Determination of Academic Performance Profile as Predictors of Licensure Exam Rating

Simple linear regression was used in determining predictors of licensure exam rating. The ANOVA was used to determine if the linear regression model is significant in predicting the dependent variable.

Assessment of Institutional Factors and the Trend in the Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate

Assessment of institutional factors was done based on the study participants responses in the questionnaire which centralizes on curriculum and instruction. The quality of curriculum and instruction were rated by the study participants based on the interpretation used in [Delos Angeles \(2020\)](#). Means and standard deviations were used and interpreted based on scales.

The quality of the curriculum were measured in terms of the degree of importance of each of the variables for the courses included in the licensure exam and were interpreted using the

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following scale: 1.00-1.49 = *Not Important*; 1.50-2.49 = *Least Important*; 2.50-3.49 = *Fairly Important*; 3.50-4.49 = *Important*; 4.50-5.00 = *Very Important*.

On the quality of instruction through instructional procedures employed by faculty, the following scale were used for interpretation: 1.00-1.49 = *Never Practiced*; 1.50-2.49 = *Seldom Practiced*; 2.50-3.49 = *Sometimes Practiced*; 3.50-4.49 = *Often Practiced*; 4.5-5.00 = *Always Practiced*.

On the quality of instruction through course requirements and on sources of written exercises administered by faculty, the scale used is as follows: .00-1.49 = *Never*; 1.50-2.49 = *Seldom*; 2.50-3.49 = *Sometimes*; 3.50-4.49 = *Often*; 4.5-5.00 = *Always*.

On the quality of instruction through availability of learning facilities, the following scale was used: 1.00-1.49 = *Not Important*; 1.50-2.49 = *Least Important*; 2.50-3.49 = *Fairly Important*; 3.50-4.49 = *Important*; 4.50-5.00 = *Very Important*.

Qualitative responses were also sought also from them to be able to identify strengths and opportunities for improvement based on their experiences as graduates of SMU.

Determination of Correlation Between the Trend in Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate and the Study Participants' Assessment of the Institutional Factors

The Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate was correlated with the study participants' assessment of the institutional factors on curriculum and instructions using Spearman's Rho correlation.

Ethical Consideration

This study was submitted for ethics review to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with address and contact information at 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines

This study satisfied the following elements of informed consent (*see Annex C: Informed Consent for Study Participants*): 1) objectives of the study (*The main objective of the study is to identify factors that influence the licensure exam performance of Saint Mary's University from SY 2016-2017 until SY 2021-2022 in the 2 board programs under the School of Health and Natural Sciences namely BS Medical Laboratory Science and BS Pharmacy*); 2) what is expected from study participants (*may we humbly request for your precious time to voluntarily be included as one among our study participants by answering the attached research questionnaire. Your honest responses shall be necessary to help us achieve valid and reliable findings which shall be used as bases for review and revision of our admission and retention policies of the 2 programs mentioned and in crafting intervention programs on curriculum and instruction to achieve high rating in future licensure exams.*), 3) expected risks and benefits (*Rest assured that this study shall not cause any harm to the participants or to any organizations as your names and responses shall be treated with utmost confidentiality and solely be used for the objectives of this study and not to be used in any other studies and for any other purposes.*) ; 4) participation in the study is voluntary (*to voluntarily be included as one among our study participants; Should you decide to withdraw your participation, your decision is highly respected*); 5) confidentiality will be protected (*names and responses shall be treated with*

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utmost confidentiality and solely be used for the objectives of this study and not to be used in any other studies and for any other purposes); and 6) the names and contact information of the persons to be contacted for questions related to the study and about one’s rights as a study participant (For more information and inquiries related to this request, you may contact any of the undersigned personally or via email). Permissions to gather data for analysis from the concerned offices or units in SMU were also secured and the above-mentioned elements for informed consent shall also be complied with (Annex D: *Informed Consent for Units from which data will be gathered*). There is no conflict of interest of the researchers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1: Academic Profile of the Exam Takers

Table 1 shows the academic profile of the exam takers. Out of the 220 exam takers from the Medical Laboratory Science, more than half (55.4%) of them got an MTLE rating ranging from 75 to 79.99, the lowest bracket. The same result was determined for the PhLE takers wherein 54% got ratings at the lowest bracket. The next rating bracket with the most number of passers is the 80-84.99 (35% for MTLE and 27.3% for PhLE), followed by the 85 to 89.99 bracket (9.1 for MTLE and 11.9 for PhLE). Only 0.5% got a rating within the 90 to 94.99 bracket for MTLE takers and none for the PhLE takers. No exam takers were able to get ratings within the highest bracket of 95 to 100% for both MTLE and PhLE.

Table 1: Licensure Exam Performance Rating and Academic Profile of the Exam Takers

Profile Variables	Categories	MLS (n=220)		Pharmacy (n=176)	
		f	%	f	%
Licensure Exam Performance Rating	95.00 to 100.00	0	0	0	0
	90.00 to 94.99	1	.5	0	0
	85.00 to 89.99	20	9.1	21	11.9
	80.00 to 84.99	77	35.0	48	27.3
	75.00 to 79.99	121	55.4	95	54.0
	Missing Data but Passed	0	0	12	6.8
CET Score	90 and above	209	95.0	159	90.3
	89 and below	11	5.0	17	9.7
GWA in College	96.00 to 99.00	0	0	0	0
	93.00 to 95.99	1	.5	0	0
	90.00 to 92.99	10	4.5	15	8.5
	87.00 to 89.99	23	10.5	34	19.3
	Below 87.00	186	84.5	127	72.2
Internship Rating	90 to 100	9	4.1	169	96.0
	80 to 89	176	80.0	7	4.0
	75 to 79	35	15.9	0	0
	Below 75	0	0	0	0
Integrated Course	90 to 100	10	4.5	11	6.3

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80 to 99	125	56.8	51	29.0
75 to 79	85	38.6	110	62.5
Below 75	0	0	2	1.1
Missing Data	0	0	2	1.1

For the academic profile of the exam takers, both MTLE (95%) and PhLE (90.3%) takers got scores of 90 and above in their CET scores. And only a small percentage had CET scores of 89 and below. This is due to the existing admission policy that only those who get 90 and above in the CET shall be admitted to the board course programs. The small percentage of having 89 and below were those who were admitted on probationary basis due to certain valid reasons and were retained in the program because they were able to meet the grades that comply with the program's retention policy.

For the GWA in college, those who had below 87 average describes most of the MTLE (85.5%) and PhLE (72.2%) takers. This means the exam takers are generally non-academic awardees during their graduation because the 87 and below GWA does not qualify students for any academic awards.

The exam takers have commendable internship ratings. A high percentage of the MTLE takers (80%) had an internship rating within 80-89 bracket and 96% of the PhLE takers had ratings within the 90-100 bracket. These findings assumes that the takers had performed well and met the required skills during their internship.

For the Integrated Course which is the in-house review, more than half of the MTLE takers (56.8%) got rating within the 80-89 bracket while most of the the PhLE takers (62.5%) got ratings within the 75-79 bracket. Very small percentages of the takers (4.5% for MTLE and 6.3 for PhLE%) got the highest bracket rating of 90-100.

Section 2: Predictors of Licensure Exam Performance Rating

Table 2 shows the academic profile variables that predict the performance in the MTLE and PhLE. All the 4 profile variables were found to be significant predictors for MTLE performance which means that high CET score, GWA, Internship Rating and Integrated Course Rating enhance high MTLE performance rating. The same findings were determined for the PhLE except for the Integrated Course Rating which was found to be not significant. This means that high grades in the Integrated Course does not imply high PhLE performance.

Table 2: Academic Profile Variables that Predict Licensure Examination Performance Rating

Profile Variable	R	R2	ANOVA	Coefficients		t	Sig.
				Constant	(PV)		
Medical Laboratory Science							
CET Score	.324*	.105	F(1,218)=25.571, p=.000	70.346	.086	5.057*	.000
GWA	.664*	.440	F(1,218)=171.556, p=.000	10.245	.825	13.098*	.000

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Internship Rating	.405*	.164	F(1,218)=42.684, p=.000	43.333	.436	6.533*	.000
Integrated Course Rating	.524*	.274	F(1,218)=82.313, p=.000	47.052	.400	9.073*	.000
Pharmacy							
CET Score	.161*	.026	F(1,162)=4.295, p=.040	73.960	.055	2.072	.040
GWA	.575*	.331	F(1,157)=77.685, p=.000	14.185	.765	8.814	.000
Internship Rating	.315*	.099	F(1,162)=17.865, p=.000	41.784	.404	4.227	.000
Integrated Course Rating	.102**	.010	F(1,160)=1.691, p=.195	74.515	.066	1.300	.195

*significant at 0.05 level of significance, **not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The results of this study imply and supports several studies that competence in academic performance predicts licensure examination performance in the health allied sciences (Balansag & Marasigan, 2019; Banua 2017; Oducado, Cendaña & Delariarte, 2019; Cabanban, 2017; Estrada et al. , 2021; Dayaganon & Limjuco, 2016; Buraphadecha, S., Chinwong, D., Thiankhanitkun, K., 2018; Spivey, Burns & Johnson, 2020; Park, Philips & Pavuluri, 2021).

The findings support the results in the analysis made by Cabanban (2017) and Estrada et al. (2021) for MTLE wherein there is a substantial correlation between academic performance and board examination results and academic performance significantly predicts MTLE. The study gets further support from results of studies of licensure exams of other health allied programs like in Banua (2017) wherein academic performance was found to be the best predictor in NLE and the College Grade General Weighted Average and scores in College Admission Test significantly correlates with NLE rating (Oducado, Cendaña and Delariarte, 2019). Similarly, the findings in this study were congruent to identifying academic performance as significant factor in terms of student internship grade for radiotechnology licensure exam in the study of Talaroc, Ali and Alipio (2021).

Also, the findings in this study are similar to the findings in studies measuring the preparedness of health allied science graduates to pass certain foreign government standard tests for employment such as the high correlation between the MT/MLS graduates' academic performance and their preparedness to American Society for Clinical Pathology (ASCP) examination (Dayaganon and Limjuco, 2016) and the college admission test and grade point average as positively correlated factors in passing the North American Pharmacist Licensure Examination (NAPLEX) (Spivey, Burns & Johnson, 2020; Park, Philips & Pavuluri, (2021).

Generally for both MTLE and PhLE, the findings in this study imply that when academic performance is high, board rating is also high. Hence, the existing admission and retention policies of the two programs may assure the exam takers to pass the licensure exams but there is a need to strictly implement these policies. It is observed that some of the exam takers were admitted even if they have the below 90 scores in the admission test. Though they passed the licensure exam, this study finds that high scores in the CET indicates high licensure performance rating. Hence, the CET cut-off for board programs must strictly be implemented. The same with GWA in college which have

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been found to be a predictor. Majority of the exam takers were described to have had a GWA of 87 and below, belonging to the bracket of non-academic awardees. Yet they passed the exam, this is a consideration that there must be strict implementation of the retention policies of the 2 programs so that those who will graduate have been strictly screened for a higher chance of getting high licensure exam ratings.

The internship rating was found to be significant predictor for both MTLE and for PhLE which gives an assumption that the more efficient learnings the MedTech and Pharmacy students get from their clinical-based internship as represented by their high internship grades, the better chance for them of getting higher scores in the MTLE. Since most of the professional subjects included in the MTLE and PhLE entail clinical-based practice, hands-on activities are important and the students learn these from their hospital-based trainings. Thus, this study finds it necessary to assure that hospital or company partners for their internship must be able to strictly cover the competencies the students need. It is also necessary that even prior to internship, their competencies in the laboratory courses where they learn the basics of clinical practice before they are deployed for a more intensive training in the partner hospitals/companies must be completely covered to better prepare them to get high scores in the MTLE.

This study finds the integrated course rating as a significant predictor for MTLE but not for PhLE. Other factors on the integrated course rating which this study has not fully covered may have led to the not significant result for the PhLE. Relating it to the responses of the study participants (see section 6a and 6b), the inhouse review (including seminar lectures) was among those mentioned as contributors for their success in passing the MTLE and PhLE and even suggested for the continuity of inhouse review and more seminar lectures. Hence, the in-house review must then be continued as part of the curriculum for both programs.

Section 3: Trend in Institutional Licensure Exam Performance

Figures 2 and 3 show the trends in the overall passing rates of the two programs against the national passing rates.

Figure 2 shows that it was in the August 2016 (100%) and February 2017 MTLE (91.47%) that the IPR is above the NPR. Going down trend is observed in the succeeding MTLEs with the lowest ratings in September 2018 and September 2019 MTLEs. In the August 2022 MTLE, the IPR (42.31%) moved closely to the NPR (47.63%) and eventually passed above (87.50%) the NPR (76.46%) in the March 2023 MTLE.

Figure 3 shows that the first batch of PhLE takers, the IPR (71.43%) was above the NPR (50.50%) and a downward trend below the NPR followed until the August 2017 PhLE. In the March 2018 PhLE, a little higher IPR (57.69%) than the NPR (55.77%) was obtained and an upward trend followed (though still lower than the NPR in the August 2018 PhLE) with a very high rating in the March 2019 PhLE (91.11%) as compared to the 64.94% NPR. However, a drastic below NPR (69.52%) rating was obtained the next exam (August 2019, 33.33%) and was followed by a far higher IPR rating (85.71%) than the NPR (66.15%) in the June 2021 PhLE. However from June 2021, the graph shows that the IPRs obtained had been consistently above the NPR until the latest

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PhLE in November 2022. Hence, for the 4 most recent PhLE, commendable performances had been obtained.

The reasons behind the trends shown by the graphs are beyond the scope of this study since these shall be taken into consideration in the next stage of the study where the non-passers are to be involved. However, with regards to the last batch of MTLE (March 2023) and the consistent above NPR results for the PhLE in the recent 4 batches (June 2021, November 2021, April 2022, November 2022), such remarkable above the NPR results may be attributed to the initiatives of the SHANS of improving the ratings through the implementation of the SHANS with ME project which is a free review session offered to the graduating students or to be exam takers to help them refreshed with topics in the licensure exams and the strict monitoring of faculty through conferencing between the department head and faculty to address issues raised by students as to their experiences in classroom instruction.

Figure 2: Institutional MTLE Passing Rate VS MTLE National Passing Rate

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Figure 3: Institutional PhLE Passing Rate VS PhLE National Passing Rate

Section 4: Assessment on the Quality of Curriculum and Instruction

Section 4a: Quality of Curriculum

Table 3 shows a summary of the study participants' assessment of the quality of curriculum.

Table 3: Curriculum Quality Factors as Assessed by the Study Participants

Curriculum Quality Factors	Mean	SD	Interpretation	
Medical Laboratory Science				
1. Attainment of Course/Subject Objectives	4.6250	.40496	Very Important	
2. Coverage of the Contents of the Course	4.6456	.39904	Very Important	
3. Quality of Instructional Materials Used	4.5456	.49819	Very Important	
4. Teachers' Mastery of the Subject Matter	4.6765	.40560	Very Important	
5. Relevance of Course Assignments or Requirements	4.4279	.56432	Important	
Overall Mean	4.5841	.37465	Very Important	
Pharmacy				
1. Attainment of Course/Subject Objectives	4.6929	.37987	Very Important	
2. Coverage of the Contents of the Course	4.6843	.37017	Very Important	
3. Quality of Instructional Materials Used	4.5983	.46692	Very Important	
4. Teachers' Mastery of the Subject Matter	4.6614	.47129	Very Important	
5. Relevance of Course Assignments or Requirements	4.5486	.50810	Very Important	
Overall Mean	4.6371	.40426	Very Important	
<i>Legend:</i>	1.00-1.49	Not Important	3.50-4.49	Important
	1.50-2.49	Least Important	4.50-5.00	Very Important

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2.50-3.49

Fairly Important

The study participants for MTLE assessed that the attainment of course objectives, coverage of the contents of the course, quality of instructional materials used and teachers' mastery of the subject matter as very important while the relevance of course assignments and requirements was assessed as "important" only. Overall, the curriculum quality factors indicated are assessed as very important (4.58) in helping them passed the exam for each of the professional courses included in the MTLE. On the other hand, the PhLE study participants assessed all the curriculum factors as very important (overall mean 4.63).

These results suggest that after having the experience of taking the exam, the participants realized that across all the professional courses in their respective curriculum, learning based on the objectives of the course, learning all the contents covered by the course, learning through the use of quality instructional materials, learning from a teacher who master the subject matter at hand and having assignments and requirements are significant factors to be able to pass the exam. Hence, these factors need be satisfied for all the professional subjects in the curriculum of both programs to best prepare the graduates to pass the licensure exam.

Section 4b: Quality of Instruction

Table 4 shows the results of the assessment of the study participants in both programs for the quality factors for instruction. For instructional procedures, all the factors were rated by both MTLE and PhLE takers as "often" (overall mean 4.12 and 4.22 respectively) for the degree of practiced by the faculty of the indicated instructional procedures for each of the professional courses included in the licensure exams.

For the course requirements, generally the study participants also from both programs rated the factors as "often" (3.90 and 3.91) for the degree of which the indicated course requirements are implemented by the faculty for each of the professional courses included in the licensure exams. The "major exam" factor however resulted in "always" (4.51) and "sometimes" (3.47) for the "portfolio" factor r for MTLE exam takers which imply that major exams were always given by the faculty and that portfolios were sometimes given as requirements in all their professional courses.

For the sources of written exercises, the results show that the study participants from both programs rated the factors as "often" (4.11 and 3.98) as to the degree of which the indicated sources of written exercises are used by the faculty for each of the professional courses. However, the PhLE takers rated "self-made exercises" as "sometimes" (3.39) implying that self-made exercises were not given by faculty most of the time.

For the availability of learning facilities, the results show that the study participants from both programs rated the factors as "important" (3.76 and 3.82) as to the degree of importance of the availability of learning facilities that helped them in passing the exam for each of the professional courses. For the MTLE study participants, they have rated the availability of the clinical laboratory to be very important (4.51) and the other facilities to a lesser extent of importance. For

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the PhLE takers, the clinical and molecular laboratories were deemed important (3.92 and 3.83) and the general laboratory and animal house facility to a lesser degree (fairly important).

Table 4: Instruction Quality Factors as Assessed by the Study Participants

Institutional Quality Factors	Medical Laboratory Science			Pharmacy		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Instructional Procedures	4.1284	.59265	Often	4.2287	.54270	Often
1. Analytical and critical thinking is promoted	4.2618	.66423	Often	4.3158	.54904	Often
2. Good attitude and appropriate techniques in learning are encourages	4.2632	.59948	Often	4.3158	.52290	Often
3. Instructional processes used are adapted to the subject matter	4.1574	.61482	Often	4.3008	.51892	Often
4. Instructional processes used are adapted to students' capability	4.1000	.63880	Often	4.2526	.53564	Often
5. Instructional processes used are adapted to situational needs	4.1029	.64922	Often	4.2556	.55232	Often
6. Instructional processes used are suited to college-level instruction	4.1868	.60887	Often	4.3068	.53132	Often
7. Instructional processes used are coordinated with library work	3.8794	.78694	Often	4.0045	.80423	Often
8. Instructional processes used are conducive to an independent study	4.0691	.63698	Often	4.1759	.56642	Often
9. Instructional processes used are related to actual life situations and practice	4.1353	.63570	Often	4.1308	.57872	Often
Course Requirements	3.9087	.68739	Often	3.9131	.61650	Often
1. Seatwork	3.8985	.74202	Often	3.9203	.64250	Often
2. Quizzes	4.2735	.57475	Often	3.8481	.67265	Often
3. Major Examinations	4.5176	.53642	Always	3.8526	.66938	Often
4. Recitation	3.7309	.87268	Often	3.8286	.66346	Often
5. Assignment	3.9809	.81043	Often	3.9128	.63594	Often
6. Oral Reports	3.5647	.96688	Often	3.8797	.63858	Often
7. Written Reports	3.7588	.89680	Often	3.9820	.55641	Often
8. Portfolio	3.4706	1.03723	Sometimes	3.9474	.63723	Often
9. Problem Sets	3.8221	.95462	Often	4.0165	.60802	Often
10. Performance Test	4.0691	.81922	Often	3.9429	.61051	Often
Sources of Written Exercises	4.1167	.66384	Often	3.9840	.48974	Often
1. Textbook	4.3353	.65921	Often	4.2150	.64490	Often
2. MTLE Review Materials	4.1765	.88438	Often	4.3459	.66944	Often
3. Self-made Exercises	3.8382	.96398	Often	3.3910	.67513	Sometimes
Availability of Learning Facilities	3.7674	.74979	Important	3.8256	.43980	Important
1. Gen Lab	4.4853	.63745	Important	4.1068	.41784	Fairly important
2. Clinical Lab	4.5118	.59212	Very important	3.9233	.58446	Important

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Institutional Quality Factors	Medical Laboratory Science			Pharmacy		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
3. Animal House	2.6078	1.20279	Least important	3.4361	.69139	Fairly important
4. Molecular Lab	3.4647	1.32606	Fairly important	3.8361	.36437	Important

Legend:

For Factors 1-3: 1.00-1.49 – Never; 1.50-2.49 – Seldom; 2.50-3.49 – Sometimes; 3.50-4.49 – Often; 4.50-5.00 – Always

For Factor 4: 1.00-1.49 – Not important ; 1.50-2.49 – Least important ; 2.50-3.49 – Fairly important ; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 4.50-5.00 – Very important

Section 5: Correlation between Institutional Licensure Exam Passing Rate and the Study Participants' Assessment on Curriculum and Instruction

Table 5 shows no significant correlation between the IPR and the study participants' assessment on curriculum for both programs. These results imply that high IPR cannot be associated with high assessment of the study participant's on the following curriculum factor variables for all the professional subjects: 1) attainment of course objectives, (2) coverage of the contents of the course, (3) quality of instructional materials used, (4) teacher's mastery of the subject matter, and (5) relevance of course assignments/requirements.

Table 6 also shows no significant correlation between the IPR and the study participants' assessment on instruction for both programs for the following curriculum factor variables: instructional procedures employed by faculty, course requirements, sources of written exercises administered by faculty and availability of learning facilities. These results imply too that high IPR cannot be associated with high assessment of the study participant's on the quality factors for instruction.

These findings generally contradicts to most of the results from other studies of similar nature (Dayaday, 2018, Delos Angeles 2020) and these can be attributed to the limited number of representatives per batch of examinees who participated in the study, that is why the overall assessment of the quality factors in relation to the IPR may not be well captured in the analysis. Despite these results, this study finds meaningful results in the study participants' responses on their assessment of the quality of curriculum as very important (see section 4a) in helping them achieve passing marks in the licensure exams. Also in their assessment for the quality of instruction (see section 4b), it was found that the availability of learning facilities are generally important to achieve passing marks. Their responses which resulted generally into "often" as to the degree of practiced by the faculty of the indicated instructional procedures, for the degree of which the

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indicated course requirements are implemented by the faculty, and for the degree of which the indicated sources of written exercises are used by the faculty are enough bases for this study to establish a more efficient process in the departments of Medical Laboratory Science and Pharmacy for monitoring classroom instruction.

Table 5: Correlational analysis between the IPR and the Assessment on Curriculum

Curriculum Quality Factors		Spearman's rho	
		Medical Laboratory Science	Pharmacy
1. Attainment of Course/Subject Objectives	Correlation Coefficient	-.493	-.239
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.087	.506
	N	13	10
2. Coverage of the Contents of the Course	Correlation Coefficient	-.540	.288
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.057	.419
	N	13	10
3. Quality of Instructional Materials Used	Correlation Coefficient	-.236	-.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.437	.688
	N	13	10
4. Teachers' Mastery of the Subject Matter	Correlation Coefficient	-.055	-.267
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.858	.455
	N	13	10
5. Relevance of Course Assignments or Requirements	Correlation Coefficient	-.267	-.061
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.378	.868
	N	13	10

Table 6: Correlational analysis between the IPR and the Assessment on Instruction

		Spearman's rho	
		Medical Laboratory Science	Pharmacy
1. Instructional Procedures	Correlation Coefficient	-.264	.394
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.384	.260
	N	13	10
2. Course Requirements	Correlation Coefficient	-.516	-.321
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.071	.365
	N	13	10
3. Sources of Written Exercises	Correlation Coefficient	-.099	-.067
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.748	.855
	N	13	10
	Correlation Coefficient	-.308	.552

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	Sig. (2-tailed)	.306	.098
4. Availability of Learning Facilities	N	13	10

Section 6: Solicited Responses on Strengths and Opportunities for Improvement

Several responses have been sought from the study participants as regards to the best contributions of SMU in their plight for passing the licensure exam and the things that they think should be taken into consideration by SMU which could have possibly made their scores higher in the licensure exam. In the context of this study, the responses were taken verbatimly as enumerated and were summarized according to their thoughts.

Section 6A: Strengths of the Institution: Best Contribution of SMU in Passing the Licensure Exam

The responses of the study participants on the strengths of SMU that they believed to have helped them in passing the licensure exams were summarized according to the following areas: instructors, review classes and seminar lectures, facilities, instruction, internship, independent learning and SMU branding.

Instructors. Responses from the study participants of both programs identified compassionate, motivating, encouraging and supportive qualities of their instructors which they believed helped them boost their stamina to pass the licensure exams. Some names of instructors were also mentioned and were described on how they were motivated by them to pass the exams.

Review classes and seminar lectures. Responses from the study participants of both programs mentioned the conduct of in-house review classes and their participation in seminar lectures as among the best contribution of the school in passing the licensure exams.

Facilities. The study participants from both programs mentioned about the availability of laboratory and library facilities of the university as among the contributors for passing the licensure exam.

Instruction. Responses from both programs mentioned of regular administration of exams and quizzes, whether short or long, announced or unannounced, as best contributory factors for passing the licensure exams. Also included are the book-based exercises and laboratory activities.

Internship. Responses of the study participants from both programs cited their actual internship practice as contributory factors.

Independent Learning. Responses of the study participants from both programs cited that they were trained for independent learning as they rely on themselves to study the materials distributed or

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referred to by their instructors. This independence made them developed critical thinking, discipline and self- trust that they can do things even with minimal supervision.

SMU branding. Responses of the study participants from both programs mentioned about the culture of excellence or quality education provided by the institution and the Marian virtues have equipped them best in passing the licensure exams.

Section 6B: Opportunities for Improvement: Factors to be taken into consideration for a Higher Passing Rate

The responses of the study participants as regards to the things that they think should be taken into consideration by SMU for them to have made their scores higher in the licensure exam. Their responses were summarized according to the following areas: instructors and their delivery of instruction, review classes and seminar lectures, facilities.

Instructors and delivery of instruction. Most of the responses from the study participants of both programs fall under their concerns on instructors and their delivery of instruction. Some of the things mentioned that needs improvement are as follows: hiring more instructors who are competent in the field, instructors must show mastery of contents of the lessons delivered, instructors must be active during discussion and not only reading the powerpoint slides, instructors to dwell more on clinical approach of teaching, more laboratory hands-on activities, more quizzes which are board exam type, and provision of quality review materials.

Review classes and seminar lectures. Responses from the study participants of both programs suggested for the continuation of the in-house review classes and the conduct of several seminar lectures on the professional subjects included in the licensure exams.

Facilities. Responses from the study participants of both programs suggested for improvement of laboratories in terms of space and equipment and acquisition of updated textbooks and review materials in the library.

CONCLUSION

The study finds the following:

1. For the academic profile of the exam takers, majority of the MTLE and PhLE takers got scores of 90 and above in their CET scores and with GWA of below 87 when they graduated in their programs. Most of the MTLE takers had an internship rating and integrated course rating

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within 80-89 bracket while the PhLE takers had their internship ratings mostly within the 90-100 bracket and within the 75-70 bracket for the integrated course rating.

2. CET score, GWA, Internship Rating and Integrated Course Rating are predictors of MTLE performance rating. The same predictors were identified for the PhLE except for the Integrated Course Rating.
3. Generally, the IPRs gained for MTLE were below the NPR. Out of the 13 MTLE batches, there were only 3 where the IPRs gained were above the NPRs with the highest rating gained in the latest MTLE. The IPRs gained for the PhLE were of inconsistent trend from the start but above NPR ratings were consistent in the 4 most recent PhLEs.
4. In the assessment of quality factors for curriculum, the MTLE and PhLE takers assessed that that across all the professional courses in their respective curriculum, the following are very important factors to be considered to be able to pass the exam: attainment of course objectives, coverage of the contents of the course, quality of instructional materials used, teachers' mastery and the relevance of course assignments and requirements. On the other hand, on the assessment of quality factors for instruction, the MTLE and PhLE takers assessed the following as "often" for each of the professional courses included in the licensure exams: degree of practiced by the faculty of the indicated instructional procedures, degree of implementation of the indicated course requirements and degree of which the indicated sources of written exercises are used by the faculty. As to the degree of importance of the availability of learning facilities that helped them in passing the exam for each of the professional courses, the MTLE and PhLE takers rated the factors generally as "important".
5. No significant correlation have been found between the IPR and the study participants's assessment on the factors for the quality of curriculum and instruction for both programs. This finding is attributed to to the limited number of representatives per batch of examinees who participated in the study, that is why the overall assessment of the quality factors in relation to the IPR may not be well captured in the analysis.
6. The best contributions of SMU to the MTLE and PhLE exam takers think have helped them pass the licensure exams were on the following areas: instructors, review classes and seminar lectures, facilities, instruction, internship, independent learning and SMU branding. The opportunities for improvement identified by the MTLE and PhLE exam takers that SMU should take into consideration are on the following areas: instructors and their delivery of instruction, review classes and seminar lectures, facilities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On Admission and Retention policies:

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1. No revision on the admission and retention policies but these must be strictly implemented..

On curriculum and instruction:

1. Intensive monitoring of faculty and their delivery of instruction by the Department Heads like regular conduct of classroom observations and faculty conferencing.
2. Continue the in-house reviews.
3. Improvement of laboratory facilities and acquisition of updated books for the professional courses included in the MTLE and PhLE.

On intervention programs:

1. Plot intervention activities which shall be included in the SHANS Action Plan which shall work on the utilization project "Intervention Activities for a Licensure Examination A+ Performance (LEAP). One of the intervention activities is to sustain the implementation of activities under the SHANS with ME project which include the conduct of free review classes and seminar lectures.

Nest stage studies:

1. A more extensive and comprehensive correlational study between licensure passing rates and curriculum and instruction with well-represented respondents from each batch of examinees.
2. A study of similar nature on the perspective on the non-passers.

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ANNEX A

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RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE FOR MEDTECH

Name (optional): _____ Sex: _____ Age: _____

Program/Course: _____

Month & Year Graduated: _____

Month & Year Licensure Exam was Taken: _____

I. Assessment of Quality of Curriculum

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Medical Technologist Licensure Exam (MTLE), rate the importance of the indicated curriculum quality factors in helping you pass the PhLE for each of the professional courses included in the MTLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = Not Important; 2 =Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important.

Professional Courses/Subjects	Curriculum Quality Factors				
	Attainment of Course/ Subject Objectives	Coverage of the Contents of the Subject	Quality of Instructional Materials Used	Teachers Mastery of the Subject Matter	The relevance of Subject Assignments/Requirement
1. Clinical Microscopy					
2. Hematology					
3. Immuno-serology					
4. Blood Banking					
5. Clinical Microbiology					
6. Parasitology					
7. Clinical Chemistry					
8. Histopathology					
9. MT Laws					
10. Laboratory Management					

Scale: 1 = Not Important; 2 =Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important

II. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Instructional Procedures employed by the Faculty

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Instruction: From your experience in taking the Medical Technologist Licensure Exam (MTLE), rate the degree of practiced by the faculty of the indicated instructional procedures for each of the professional courses included in the MTLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = Never Practiced; 2 = Seldom Practiced; 3 = Sometimes Practiced; 4 = Often Practiced; 5 = Always Practiced.

Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Instructional Procedures								
	Analytical and critical thinking is promoted	Good attitude and appropriate techniques in learning are encouraged	Instructional processes used are adapted to the subject matter	Instructional processes used are adapted to students' capability	Instructional processes used are adapted to situational needs	Instructional processes used are suited to college-level instruction	Instructional processes used are coordinated with library work	Instructional processes used are conducive to an independent study	Instructional processes used are related to actual life situations and practice
1. Clinical Microscopy									
2. Hematology									
3. Immuno-serology									
4. Blood Banking									
5. Clinical Microbiology									
6. Parasitology									
7. Clinical Chemistry									
8. Histopathology									
9. MT Laws									
10. Laboratory Management									

Scale: 1 = Never Practiced; 2 = Seldom Practiced; 3 = Sometimes Practiced; 4 = Often Practiced; 5 = Always Practiced

III. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Course Requirements

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Medical Technologist Licensure Exam (MTLE), rate the degree of which the indicated course requirements are implemented by the faculty for each of

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the professional courses included in the MTLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = *Never*; 2 = *Seldom*; 3 = *Sometimes*; 4 = *Often*; 5 = *Always*..

Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Course Requirements									
	Seatwork	Quizzes	Major Examinations	Recitation	Assignments	Oral Reports	Written Reports	Portfolio	Problem Sets	Performance Test
1. Clinical Microscopy										
2. Hematology										
3. Immunoserology										
4. Blood Banking										
5. Clinical Microbiology										
6. Parasitology										
7. Clinical Chemistry										
8. Histopathology										
9. MT Laws										
10. Laboratory Management										

Scale: 1 = *Never*; 2 = *Seldom*; 3 = *Sometimes*; 4 = *Often*; 5 = *Always*

IV. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Written Exercises Administered by Faculty

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Medical Technologist Licensure Exam (MTLE), rate the degree of which the indicated sources of written exercises are used by the faculty for each of the professional courses included in the MTLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = *Never*; 2 = *Seldom*; 3 = *Sometimes*; 4 = *Often*; 5 = *Always*..

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Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Sources of Written Exercises		
	Textbook	PhLE Review Materials	Self-made Exercises
1. Clinical Microscopy			
2. Hematology			
3. Immuno-serology			
4. Blood Banking			
5. Clinical Microbiology			
6. Parasitology			
7. Clinical Chemistry			
8. Histopathology			
9. MT Laws			
10. Laboratory Management			

Scale: 1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always

V. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Availability of Learning Facilities

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Medical Technologist Licensure Exam (MTLE), rate the importance of the availability of learning facilities which helped you in passing the exam for each of the professional courses included in the MTLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = Not Important; 2 = Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important.

Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Availability of Learning Facilities			
	General Laboratory Room	Clinical Laboratory	Animal House Facility	Molecular Laboratory
1. Clinical Microscopy				
2. Hematology				
3. Immuno-serology				
4. Blood Banking				
5. Clinical Microbiology				
6. Parasitology				
7. Clinical Chemistry				
8. Histopathology				
9. MT Laws				
10. Laboratory Management				

Scale: 1 = Not Important; 2 = Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important.

VI. Strengths and Opportunities for Improvement

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Instruction: Give honest answers for the following questions based on your experiences in taking BSP in SMU.

1. What do you think is the best contribution of SMU in your success of passing the MTLE?
2. What other factors should SMU look into that you think could even make your Licensure Exam score higher than what you obtained?

**ANNEX B
THE RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PHARMACY**

Name (optional): _____ Sex: _____ Age: _____
 Program/Course: _____
 Month & Year Graduated: _____
 Month & Year Licensure Exam was Taken: _____

I. Assessment of Quality of Curriculum

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Instruction: From your experience in taking the Pharmacist Licensure Exam (PhLE), rate the importance of the indicated curriculum quality factors in helping you pass the PhLE for each of the professional courses included in the PhLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: *1 = Not Important; 2 = Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important.*

Professional Courses/Subjects	Curriculum Quality Factors				
	Attainment of Course/Subject Objectives	Coverage of the Contents of the Subject	Quality of Instructional Materials Used	Teachers Mastery of the Subject Matter	The relevance of Subject Assignments/Requirement
1. Inorganic Pharmaceutical Chemistry					
2. Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry					
3. Pharmacognosy and Plant Chemistry					
4. Biochemistry					
5. Compounding and Dispensing Pharmacy					
6. Clinical Pharmacy					
7. Hospital Pharmacy					
8. Pharmaceutical Calculations					
9. Biopharmaceutics					
10. Pharmacology					
11. Toxicology					
12. Incompatibilities and Adverse Drug Reactions					
13. Manufacturing Pharmacy					
14. Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms					

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15. Physical Pharmacy					
16. Jurisprudence and Ethics					
17. Microbiology					
18. Public Health					
19. Quality Control					

Scale: 1 = Not Important; 2 =Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important

II. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Instructional Procedures employed by the Faculty

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Pharmacist Licensure Exam (PhLE), rate the degree of practiced by the faculty of the indicated instructional procedures for each of the professional courses included in the PhLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = Never Practiced; 2 =Seldom Practiced; 3 = Sometimes Practiced; 4 = Often Practiced; 5 = Always Practiced.

Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Instructional Procedures								
	Analytical and critical thinking is promoted	Good attitude and appropriate techniques in learning are encouraged	Instructional processes used are adapted to the subject matter	Instructional processes used are adapted to students' capability	Instructional processes used are adapted to situational needs	Instructional processes used are suited to college-level instruction	Instructional processes used are coordinated with library work	Instructional processes used are conducive to an independent study	Instructional processes used are related to actual life situations and practice
1. Inorganic Pharmaceutical Chemistry									
2. Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry									
3. Pharmacognosy and Plant Chemistry									
4. Biochemistry									
5. Compounding and Dispensing Pharmacy									
6. Clinical Pharmacy									

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7. Hospital Pharmacy										
8. Pharmaceutical Calculations										
9. Biopharmaceutics										
10. Pharmacology										
11. Toxicology										
12. Incompatibilities and Adverse Drug Reactions										
13. Manufacturing Pharmacy										
14. Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms										
15. Physical Pharmacy										
16. Jurisprudence and Ethics										
17. Microbiology										
18. Public Health										
19. Quality Control										

Scale: 1 = Never Practiced; 2 = Seldom Practiced; 3 = Sometimes Practiced; 4 = Often Practiced; 5 = Always Practiced

III. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Course Requirements

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Pharmacist Licensure Exam (PhLE), rate the degree of which the indicated course requirements are implemented by the faculty for each of the professional courses included in the PhLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always.

Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Course Requirements									
	Seatwork	Quizzes	Major Examinations	Recitation	Assignments	Oral Reports	Written Reports	Portfolio	Problem Sets	Performance Test
1. Inorganic Pharmaceutical Chemistry										
2. Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry										
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4. Biochemistry										
5. Compounding and Dispensing Pharmacy										
6. Clinical Pharmacy										

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7. Hospital Pharmacy											
8. Pharmaceutical Calculations											
9. Biopharmaceutics											
10. Pharmacology											
11. Toxicology											
12. Incompatibilities and Adverse Drug Reactions											
13. Manufacturing Pharmacy											
14. Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms											
15. Physical Pharmacy											
16. Jurisprudence and Ethics											
17. Microbiology											
18. Public Health											
19. Quality Control											

Scale: 1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always

IV. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Written Exercises Administered by Faculty

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Pharmacist Licensure Exam (PhLE), rate the degree of which the indicated sources of written exercises are used by the faculty for each of the professional courses included in the PhLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always. .

Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Sources of Written Exercises		
	Textbook	PhLE Review Materials	Self-made Exercises
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2. Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry			
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4. Biochemistry			

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5. Compounding and Dispensing Pharmacy			
6. Clinical Pharmacy			
7. Hospital Pharmacy			
8. Pharmaceutical Calculations			
9. Biopharmaceutics			
10. Pharmacology			
11. Toxicology			
12. Incompatibilities and Adverse Drug Reactions			
13. Manufacturing Pharmacy			
14. Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms			
15. Physical Pharmacy			
16. Jurisprudence and Ethics			
17. Microbiology			
18. Public Health			
19. Quality Control			

Scale: 1 = Never; 2 =Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always

V. Assessment of Quality of Instruction through Availability of Learning Facilities

Instruction: From your experience in taking the Pharmacist Licensure Exam (PhLE), rate the importance of the availability of learning facilities which helped you in passing the exam for each of the professional courses included in the PhLE. Rate the factors using the scale 1 to 5: 1 = Not Important; 2 =Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important.

Professional Courses/Subjects	Instruction Quality Factors through Availability of Learning Facilities			
	General Laboratory Room	Clinical Laboratory	Animal House Facility	Molecular Laboratory
1. Inorganic Pharmaceutical Chemistry				
2. Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry				
3. Pharmacognosy and Plant Chemistry				
4. Biochemistry				
5. Compounding and Dispensing Pharmacy				
6. Clinical Pharmacy				

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7. Hospital Pharmacy				
8. Pharmaceutical Calculations				
9. Biopharmaceutics				
10. Pharmacology				
11. Toxicology				
12. Incompatibilities and Adverse Drug Reactions				
13. Manufacturing Pharmacy				
14. Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms				
15. Physical Pharmacy				
16. Jurisprudence and Ethics				
17. Microbiology				
18. Public Health				
19. Quality Control				

Scale: 1 = Not Important; 2 =Least Important; 3 = Fairly Important; 4 = Important; 5 = Very Important.

VI. Strengths and Opportunities for Improvement

Instruction: Give honest answers for the following questions based on your experiences in taking BSP in SMU.

1. What do you think is the best contribution of SMU in your success of passing the PhLE?
2. What other factors should SMU look into that you think could even make your Licensure Exam score higher than what you obtained?

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ANNEX C
INFORMED CONSENT FOR STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Dear Study Participants,

Greetings from Saint Mary's University!

The undersigned are researchers from the School of Health and Natural Science of Saint Mary's University conducting a study entitled "SHANS - LOOKING BACK AND BEYOND: INFLUENTIAL FACTORS IN LICENSURE EXAM PERFORMANCE FOR MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE AND PHARMACY". The main objective of the study is to identify factors that influence the licensure exam performance of Saint Mary's University from SY 2016-2017 until SY 2021-2022 in the 2 board programs under the School of Health and Natural Sciences namely BS Medical Laboratory Science and BS Pharmacy. In this anent, may we humbly request for your precious time during the data gathering months of our study (January-March) to voluntarily be included as one among our study participants by answering the attached research questionnaire. Your honest responses shall be necessary to help us achieve valid and reliable findings which shall be used as bases for review and revision of our admission and retention policies of the 2 programs mentioned and in crafting intervention programs on curriculum and instruction to achieve high rating in future licensure exams. Rest assured that this study shall not cause any harm to the participants or to any organizations as your names and responses shall be treated with utmost confidentiality and solely be used for the objectives of this study and not to be used in any other studies and for any other purposes. Should you decide to withdraw your participation, your decision is highly respected.

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For more information and inquiries related to this request, you may contact any of the undersigned personally or via email.

Respectfully yours,

DR. ARLENE L. TABAQUERO
Email: atabaquero@smu.edu.ph

MRS. MELCHORA M. BAUTISTA
Email: mbautista@smu.edu.ph

MRS. SHIELA M. RAMOS
Email: sramos@smu.edu.ph

Name and Signature of the Participant

ANNEX D
INFORMED CONSENT FOR UNITS WHERE DATA WILL BE GATHERED

(Name of the Head of Office)
(Position of the Head of Office)
Saint Mary's University
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Dear Sir/Madam,

Marian Greetings!

The undersigned are researchers from the School of Health and Natural Science of Saint Mary's University conducting a study entitled "SHANS - LOOKING BACK AND BEYOND: INFLUENTIAL FACTORS IN LICENSURE EXAM PERFORMANCE FOR MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE AND PHARMACY". The main objective of the study is to identify factors that influence the licensure exam performance of Saint Mary's University from SY 2016-2017 until SY 2021-2022 in the 2 board programs under the School of Health and Natural Sciences namely BS Medical Laboratory Science and BS Pharmacy.

In this anent, may we humbly seek permission from your office to provide us the following data which are needed in our study:

Your participation in this study as providers of the data we need is deeply appreciated and acknowledged. The data will be necessary to help us achieve valid and reliable findings which shall be used as bases for review and revision of our admission and retention policies of the 2 programs mentioned and in crafting intervention programs on curriculum and instruction to achieve high rating in future licensure exams. Rest assured that the data shall be treated with utmost confidentiality and solely be used for the objectives of this study and not to be used in any other studies and for any other purposes.

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For more information and inquiries related to this request, you may contact any of the undersigned personally or via email.

Respectfully yours,

DR. ARLENE L. TABAQUERO
Email: atabaquero@smu.edu.ph

MRS. MELCHORA M. BAUTISTA
Email: mbautista@smu.edu.ph

Name and Signature of the Participant/Data Provider

MRS. SHIELA M. RAMOS
Email: sramos@smu.edu.ph

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OFFICE OF THE PRESIDENT
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH ETHICS OFFICE

CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL

This certifies that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the SMUREB for implementation.

SMUREB Code: 1sem 2022 199

Research Proponent: ARLENE L. TABAQUERO

Title: SHANS-Looking Back and Beyond: Factors that Influence the Licensure Exam Performance for Medical Laboratory Science and Pharmacy

Protocol Version No.: 2

Version Date: January 11, 2023

ICF Version No.: 2

Version Date: January 11, 2023

Type of Review: EXPEDITED

Validity: 12 months

Responsibilities of the research proponent after approval:

1. Submit application for review of amendments (REB-FO-010) if there is a need to change the protocol which may significantly impact the human participants.
2. Submit a report of any deviations/violations of the protocol or data gathering procedure (REB-FO-012) and report of any negative events affecting the integrity of data gathering procedure from participants (REB-FO-013).
3. Submit application for continuing review (REB-FO-014) if the research project is not yet completed within the validity period of this ethics clearance.
4. Submit early termination report (REB-FO-016) if the research project will be discontinued.
5. Submit final report (REB-FO-017) after completion of the research project. This is mandatory. The research proponent will be given a final ethics clearance certificate that will be attached on the final bound copy of the research/thesis.

This certification is valid until January 11, 2024.

Issued and signed on January 11, 2023 by

JASON ARNOLD L. MASLANG
 Chair, SMUREB

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